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National Awakening in Azerbaijan in the 50-60s of the XX Century

Abstract

The article explores the key aspects of the policy implemented by the totalitarian Soviet regime in Azerbaijan during the 1950s and 1960s, as well as the socio-political dynamics in the country and the trends of national revival. It analyzes the National Awakening in Azerbaijan, the rise of chauvinism from the center, punitive actions against the Republic's leadership and nationalistic intellectuals, and the efforts by Armenians to exploit the situation to oppress Azerbaijanis in Armenian SSR, which fueled separatist sentiments among Armenians in Azerbaijan SSR. Despite the ideological pressure and repression from the Soviet regime, the article highlights the efforts of opposition-minded individuals to organize amidst the growing national consciousness among the intelligentsia and youth, fostering a critical stance towards the existing regime. The National Awakening that took place in Azerbaijan during the 1950s and 1960s was crucial not only for preserving the traditions of national statehood and passing them on to future generations but also for laying the groundwork for the struggle for independence.

Keywords: Totalitarian Regime, Deportation, National Revival, Native Language, National Self-Awareness

XX. Yüzyılın 50-60'lı Yıllarında Azerbaycan'da Ulusal Uyanış

Öz

Bu makale, 1950'li ve 1960'lı yıllarda Azerbaycan'da totaliter Sovyet rejimi tarafından uygulanan politikanın temel yönlerini, ülkedeki sosyo-politik dinamikleri ve ulusal uyanış eğilimlerini incelemektedir. Azerbaycan'daki Ulusal Uyanış, merkezden yükselen şovenizm, Cumhuriyetin

liderliğine ve milliyetçi entelektüellere karşı cezalandırma eylemleri ve Azerbaycan SSC'deki Ermeniler arasında ayrılıkçı duyguları körükleyen Ermenilerin Ermenistan SSC'deki Azerilere baskı yapmak için durumu istismar etme çabaları analiz edilmektedir. Makale, Sovyet rejiminin ideolojik baskı ve zulmüne rağmen, muhalif düşünen bireylerin, aydınlar ve gençler arasında artan ulusal bilincin ortasında örgütlenme çabalarını ve mevcut rejime karşı eleştirel bir duruşu teşvik ettiğini vurgulamaktadır. Azerbaycan'da 1950'ler ve 1960'larda gerçekleşen Milli Uyanış, sadece milli devlet geleneklerinin korunması ve gelecek nesillere aktarılması açısından değil, aynı zamanda bağımsızlık mücadelesine zemin hazırlaması açısından da büyük önem taşımaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Totaliter Rejim, Sürgün, Milli Uyanış, Anadil, Milli Benlik Bilinci

Introduction

The primary aim of the Soviet regime in Azerbaijan was to disconnect the people from their history, cultural heritage, traditions, and religious beliefs, ultimately creating individuals who embodied the values of the newly formed socialist society. In the Turkic-Muslim republics of the USSR, this policy was implemented more rigorously than in other regions. The deportation of Azerbaijanis from the Armenian SSR during the late 1940s and early 1950s by the Soviet regime stands as one of the most significant tragedies faced by the Azerbaijani people in the 20th century. Following the leadership change in the Soviet Union in 1953, reforms initiated in Azerbaijan, along with the active involvement of the intelligentsia, aimed to preserve the native language and national cultural values within the existing framework. This effort, while putting immense pressure on the Union's leadership, also served as a catalyst for change.

1. National awakening in Azerbaijan in the 50-60s of the XX century

The Russian Empire aimed to establish ethnic and socio-economic control in the northern part of Azerbaijan. Throughout the century that Azerbaijan was part of the Empire, areas populated by Azerbaijanis were incorporated into various administrative units created in the South Caucasus. Due to the Empire's resettlement policy, a significant number of Armenians were relocated to the Yerevan, Nakhchivan, and Karabakh regions of Azerbaijan, while Russians were settled in the Mughan and Shirvan areas. The primary objective of Tsarist Russia's policy was to erase the Azerbaijanis' national and cultural identity, effectively assimilating them. This resettlement strategy resulted in significant demographic shifts within Azerbaijan.

Despite the resettlement policies implemented by Tsarist Russia, the Azerbaijani people continued to be the predominant group in the country's ethnic and religious makeup. They remained in their historical territories, maintaining their mentality, cultural heritage, ethnic

identity, and religious tolerance, while also contributing uniquely to the blending of Eastern and Western cultures (Azərbaycan multikulturalizmi, 2017). The development of capitalist relations in Azerbaijan led to a heightened sense of national self-awareness and the emergence of the Azerbaijani nation. This shift highlighted the failures of Tsarist Russia, which aimed to assimilate the Turkic-Muslim population in the South Caucasus by introducing Christian elements, such as Germans and Russians, and through the mass resettlement of Armenians.

In 1917, the Russian Empire collapsed, and by 1918, Azerbaijan restored its statehood after nearly a century. During the brief existence of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic from 1918 to 1920, significant strides were made in safeguarding national and moral values and reinforcing statehood. However, this independence was short-lived due to the occupation by Bolshevik Russia. Following the Soviet occupation in 1920, Azerbaijan was nominally independent, but by 1922, it became part of the newly formed USSR.

Within the Soviet Union, communism was the official ideology, leading to the establishment of a new social structure—a socialist society. The aim was to create an artificial union known as the Soviet people from the various ethnic groups within the USSR. This new union primarily reflected the values of the Russian-Slavic peoples, resulting in the suppression of the national and spiritual values of the Turkic-speaking populations. False internationalism was promoted, and to disrupt historical continuity, the Azerbaijani alphabet was changed twice in a short span, transitioning to Cyrillic script. In the 1920s and 1930s, the socialist perestroika significantly undermined national values, leading to a stronger push for unification. The Communist Party of the Soviet Union exerted strict control over state institutions, the judiciary, and public organizations, steering societal development to align with its objectives.

The communists' approach to their so-called "humane, caring" national policy was fundamentally rooted in a dominant form of nationalism. This was implemented by managing assimilation, altering the ethnic makeup of national republics through deliberate migration strategies, establishing a mandatory unified means of communication, and maintaining all potential sources of conflict that could be activated when needed (Orucov, 2001). The USSR maintained the old imperial traditions, even though it was ideologically very different from Tsarist Russia. While the leaders of the empire promoted the idea of "friendship of peoples," they actually implemented discriminatory policies against non-Russians in the USSR, particularly targeting the Turkic-Muslim communities. Capitalizing on this environment, the leadership of Soviet Armenia frequently brought up the issue of transferring the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region from Azerbaijan to the Armenian SSR during the Soviet era.

In the fall of 1945, Arutinov, the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Armenia, made a request to the central committee of the UIC(b)P regarding the incorporation of the Nagorno–Karabakh Autonomous Region into the Armenian SSR (Aliyev, 1989). The center received an appeal from Armenian officials to Azerbaijan regarding their stance on the incorporation of the NKAO into the Armenian SSR.

M. J. Bagirov, the head of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan, states that he is willing to transfer Upland Karabakh to Armenia, with the exception of the Shusha region, which has a predominantly Azerbaijani population. These are contingent upon the inclusion of three regions in Armenia that border Azerbaijan and are mainly inhabited by Azerbaijanis into Azerbaijan (Aliyev, 1989). M. J. Bagirov's decision to include the Vedi, Azizbeyov and Garabagh districts of the Armenian SSR into the Azerbaijan SSR raised concerns not only in Armenia but also among the Soviet leadership, which feared the potential unity of the Turkic peoples. Transferring these regions to Azerbaijan would undermine the strategy of the USSR in the South Caucasus, particularly the establishment of the Zangazur corridor aimed at separating Turkey from Azerbaijan. Influenced by the Armenian Lobby in Moscow, the Soviet leadership implemented measures to further reinforce this corridor. As a result, Azerbaijanis faced mass deportations from western Azerbaijan (Armenian SSR) during the 20th century, specifically between 1948 and 1953, based on decisions made by the USSR government.

On December 23, 1947, the Council of Ministers of the USSR made a decision regarding the resettlement of collective farmers and other Azerbaijani people from the Armenian SSR to the Kur-Araz lowland in the Azerbaijan SSR. Then, on March 10, 1948, another resolution outlined a specific action plan to carry out this initiative (XX əsr Azərbaycan tarixi, 2004). During this period of ethnic cleansing from the Armenian SSR, over 100,000 Azerbaijanis were either forcibly resettled or compelled to leave their homes (Mustafazadə, 1998). About one in three individuals relocated from the mountainous areas of Armenia to the Kur-Araz Valley in Azerbaijan. Many struggled to adapt to the new environment, characterized by a hot and dry climate, and faced issues related to domestic security, leading to deaths from hunger and disease. Moscow achieved its objective: the population of Azerbaijanis in Armenia significantly declined. Concurrently, Armenian expansion into the western regions of Azerbaijan—such as Dashkasan, Goranboy, Shamkir, Ganja, Nagorno-Karabakh and Baku—intensified (Mustafazadə, 1998). The Soviet leadership, following Imperial traditions, persisted in the policy of pushing Azerbaijanis out of the Republic of Armenia, which was established in the South Caucasus on historically Azerbaijani lands. Simultaneously, by increasing the Armenian

population in the western regions of the Azerbaijan SSR, they set the stage for future territorial claims by Armenians to these areas. The fate of tens of thousands of individuals who were relocated from their ancestral lands in western Azerbaijan and the Armenian SSR to the lowland regions of the Azerbaijan SSR was tragic.

National leader H. Aliyev remarked that *"the policy of genocide carried out by Armenian nationalists in the 1940s and 1950s, taking advantage of the Soviet regime, brought new tragedies to the Azerbaijani people"* (Azərbaycan multikulturalizmi, 2017, s. 128). Similar to the situation in Baku during the 1920s and 1930s, the resettlement of non-Azerbaijanis, particularly Armenians, to the new industrial centers established in the 1940s and 1950s highlighted the true nature of the national policy of the Soviet empire. Following the Bolshevik occupation of the South Caucasus, Armenians actively participated in the colonial policies of the Soviet regime, just as they had in the Russian Empire. Those Armenians in prominent positions in Azerbaijan were particularly noted for fostering discord among national groups and repressing the Azerbaijani intelligentsia. After the change of leadership in the Soviet Union in 1953, significant transformations started to take place in the country. Reforms aimed at addressing the negative aspects of the totalitarian regime, which had resulted in violations of citizens' rights and widespread repression. Following Stalin's reign, in June 1953, L.P. Beria was arrested, marking the beginning of a personnel shift in the country that also affected Azerbaijan. In countries with a one-party political system, the personal attributes of the leader play a crucial role in governance. Imam Mustafayev, who has been at the helm of Azerbaijan since 1954, maximized the impact of reforms and a moderate policy to improve the living standards of the population while also safeguarding national values.

Hundreds of Azerbaijanis were branded as "enemies of the people" Many statesmen, as well as figures from literature and the arts, including Huseyn Javid, Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli, and Mikayil Mushfig, were eventually acquitted. The monumental heroic epic "Kitab-Dede Gorgud," which holds significant value in terms of history, literary language, folklore, and the ethnography of the Azerbaijani Turks, was dismissed as a promoter of feudal-bourgeois and non-constructive ideas. Numerous "banned" books, including the works of A. A. Bakikhanov and academician Heydar Huseynov, were published. The writings of several poets and authors who were acquitted also saw the light of day (Zeynalov, 2004). Not all victims of repression were acquitted during the acquittal process. While mainly party members and statesmen were acquitted, many in the intelligentsia were not, and thousands of political activists remained unacquitted, including those who were forced into exile, those who fought

for Azerbaijan's independence, and those who opposed the Soviet regime. The repressed writer Huseyn Javid's plays, "Lame Timur" and "Prophet," were intentionally forgotten by the Soviet authorities. Bans on these works remained in place because they, along with other artistic expressions about Azerbaijan's and Turkey's history, were seen as a threat to Soviet ideology. It wasn't until the second half of the 1980s, during the "perestroika" reforms in the USSR, that the acquittal process finally came to a close.

The acquittal processes continued in 1957. While most of the repressed groups were acquitted, the exiled Azerbaijani, Greek, and Bulgarian communities were not granted acquittal (Mustafazadə, 1998). The union leadership showed no interest in bringing this process to a close. At this time, representatives of certain groups were either "forgotten" or dismissed, while the exiled Crimean Tatars, the Ahilasa Turks, and the repressed Azerbaijanis were still barred from returning to their homeland. The fact that the USSR leadership had no intention of ending this situation reveals the true nature of Soviet national policy. The leadership of the Republic took significant steps to restore the rights of Azerbaijanis who had been repressed during World War II, utilizing this process on a union-wide scale.

On August 12, 1957, I. Mustafayev appealed to the Central Committee of the CPSU, requesting permission to return Azerbaijanis who had been deported from the Georgian SSR in 1944. However, the Georgian leadership opposed their return, leading the USSR leadership to deny their repatriation as well. On October 2, 1957 after I. Mustafayev's second appeal to the Central Committee of the CPSU, the Soviet leadership permitted the deported Azerbaijanis to return not to Georgia but to Azerbaijan. As a result of the actions taken by the Republican authorities, over 13,000 Azerbaijanis made their way back to Azerbaijan (Gasany, 2009). Under Mustafayev's leadership, the Azerbaijani authorities demonstrated a growing concern for the well-being of Azerbaijanis both within the Republic and abroad, reflecting a heightened sense of national pride in the country. During this period, there was a notable resurgence in the public life of Azerbaijan. In the Soviet Union, Russian served as the primary means of clerical and official communication, leading to a decline in the use of national languages and the erasure of non-Russian identities from their own histories and cultures. Amid a growing focus on national and cultural values, the status of the Azerbaijani language became a significant topic among the intelligentsia. During this time, the prominent writer Mirza Ibrahimov authored his book "Azerbaijani Language".

In a moderately stable socio-political climate, an initiative was launched to establish the Azerbaijani language as the official state language of the Republic. This issue was openly

discussed in the media for the first time, highlighting the significance of the Azerbaijani language's new status (Mustafazadə, 1998). Previous attempts to achieve this had been made during Bagirov's era in the late 1940s and early 1950s (Gasanlı, 2009).

In 1956, the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR amended the Constitution of the Azerbaijan SSR, originally adopted in 1937, to declare Azerbaijani as the state language of the Republic. This language law fostered a sense of national pride among the intelligentsia and the general populace, particularly in Baku, which is home to many non-Azerbaijanis. The growing Azerbaijani population contributed to the “nationalization” of Baku, an international city. In the early 1950s, the population of Azerbaijanis in Baku was only slightly greater than that of non-Azerbaijanis. One of the significant achievements of the leadership of the Republic under Mustafayev was the effort made to boost the number of Azerbaijanis living in Baku.

Thanks to the effective social and economic policies implemented by the leadership of the Republic, Baku's industrial development picked up pace, leading to the creation of numerous new jobs. Young people from rural areas of Azerbaijan were drawn to these opportunities. As a result, the population of Azerbaijanis in Baku grew significantly, altering the demographic landscape. The presence of Azerbaijani professionals in both the economic and public spheres of the capital increased, positively influencing the socio-political environment. Baku, recognized as an international city, began its journey towards greater Azerbaijani identity (Azərbaycan tarixi, 2008). N. S. Khrushchev's plan to detach the International City of Baku from Azerbaijan and establish it as an independent administrative unit under central control was ultimately unsuccessful. The Soviet leadership's efforts to separate Baku from Azerbaijan, spurred on by Armenian interests, did not come to fruition.

As a result of reforms implemented by the Soviet leadership in the mid-1950s, the rights of the allied republics were somewhat expanded. In this context, the initiatives aimed at elevating the status of national languages were viewed as part of the ongoing reforms; however, the introduction of a language law in Azerbaijan was met with disapproval from the central authorities. It became clear that the policy of granting more rights to the republics was largely superficial, and the USSR leadership did not anticipate such developments. When the law on the Azerbaijani language was adopted, Imam Mustafayev, who was the head of the Republic, was ousted from his position in the Union in 1959. This law's adoption was highlighted as one of the primary “shortcomings” of the Republic.

It is not surprising that the book “Essays on the History of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan” published in Baku in 1963 and reflecting the official stance of the USSR

leadership, mentions that there is no necessity to adopt a law on the state language (Ocherki, Istorii Kommunisticheskoy partii Ayerbaydzhana, 1963). With the enforcement of the law, national self-awareness and consciousness began to flourish in Azerbaijan. The voice that expresses proud sentiments was, in reality, a genuine struggle for the true independence of Azerbaijan and for the rights of a people whose national and economic freedoms were restricted by the central authority (Zeynalov, 2004). The key figure behind the adoption of the law on the Azerbaijani language was the distinguished writer Mirza Ibrahimov, who served as the chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR.

In his book “Azerbaijani Language,” written during that time, he emphasized that the Azerbaijani language has valiantly resisted various forms of oppression for centuries and has always emerged victorious. Centuries ago, this language was the medium for some of the most exquisite gems of world literature and significant scientific achievements (Zeynalov, 2004). After the law was adopted, specific measures were implemented to carry out official documents and clerical tasks in the Azerbaijani language. This initiative received strong backing from the creative intelligentsia and the youth of Azerbaijan.

Khrushchev's liberal reforms, particularly the issuance of passports to the rural population starting in 1955, along with the adoption and implementation of the law on the state language, spurred a movement of Russians back to central Russia in the mid-50s. This included Christian sectarians who had been resettled in Azerbaijan due to the colonial policies of Tsarist Russia. To counter this trend, the Soviet leadership initiated an extensive discussion regarding the state language law enacted in Azerbaijan, as it was seen as a measure to curb a process that was unfavorable to Moscow (Gasanly, 2009). The efforts made by the Union's leadership to halt the decrease in the Russian-speaking population—an essential foundation of the center in Azerbaijan since the era of Tsarist Russia and throughout the Soviet Union—did not yield the anticipated outcomes.

The non-Azerbaijani population in the Republic, particularly in Baku, protested against this law and began voicing their complaints to Moscow due to the rushed implementation. The dissatisfaction among non-Azerbaijanis further irritated Moscow. In response, Moscow decided to step in. While various justifications were offered, the primary reason for the center's negative stance towards the Republic's leadership was the rise of national-revival movements in Azerbaijan. As a result of this mounting pressure, Mirza Ibrahimov was dismissed from his position as Chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR in January

1958, at his own request. Six months later, S. Rahimov, the chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, was also removed from his position.

The plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU, which took place from June 24 to 29 in 1959, delivered a strong criticism of the leadership in the Azerbaijani SSR based on unfounded accusations. During the XI plenum of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan, held in July 1959, I. D. Mustafayev was dismissed (Azərbaycan tarixi, 2008). His removal from office was primarily attributed to charges of nationalism.

National leader H. Aliyev, on February 23, 1995, congratulated Mustafayev on his 85th anniversary. He remarked that *"The Azerbaijani people recognize you as a distinguished scientist and a notable public figure who dedicated your life to advancing various areas of agriculture, a true patriot who committed your efforts to serving your homeland and its people"* (Aliyev, 1997, s. 211). The leadership of the USSR was worried about the increasing national awakening in Azerbaijan, similar to what was happening in some other Union republics. The reforms implemented by the central government in the mid-50s, along with efforts to democratize socialist society, unexpectedly fueled the rise of national revival movements in the South Caucasus and Baltic republics. In Azerbaijan, national and democratic sentiments were also on the rise. However, Moscow was unprepared for this shift in dynamics.

The national awakening trends seen in the Union republics, particularly in the Azerbaijan SSR, during the mid-50s, raised significant concerns about the chauvinism originating from the Center (Mustafazadə, 1998). The events that followed demonstrated that Moscow was prepared to engage in various provocations and underhanded tactics to thwart the national movement and any actions that might foster national revival (Xudiyev, 1997). The center had already moved away from "liberal" reforms, but national revival trends were on the rise in Azerbaijan, bolstered by the Republican leadership. N. Khrushchev, who had solidified his personal power, increased pressure on the national republics. Consequently, there were changes in leadership across several Union republics in 1959. Compared to other republics, the resistance in Azerbaijan was particularly intense, as nationalism there was more pronounced. Alongside the leadership changes in Azerbaijan, the center sought to instill fear among the populace. On Mikoyan's initiative, the issue of Nagorno-Karabakh was once again brought to the forefront. The Armenian population in the Armenian SSR and the NKAO of the Azerbaijan SSR began to push for the transfer of Nagorno-Karabakh to Armenia. Anti-Turkish feelings resurfaced in Armenia. The Azerbaijani departments at the Yerevan Pedagogical Institute were shut down, and the Yerevan Azerbaijan pedagogical college was relocated to the Khanlar (Goygol) region

of Azerbaijan. Additionally, the Drama Theater named after Jabbarli, along with regional newspapers published in Azerbaijani and other publications were also closed. The "Karabakh movement" gained significant legal recognition in Armenia (Azərbaycan tarixi, 2008). Under the USSR, Moscow actively "encouraged" national conflicts to the extent that they were managed. However, when these conflicts began to undermine the state, intervention occurred. The Soviet leadership required conflicts that not only influenced their authority but also diminished internal dissent (Həsənov, 2009). In the Soviet Empire, particularly in the Caucasus, there were numerous disputed borders and potential flashpoints for national conflict. During the 1950s, Soviet leaders linked the country's issues to the lawlessness that had emerged during the era of the "personality cult." As a result, the central government rejected the Armenian leadership's proposals, fearing that the territorial claims of Armenians intertwined with those of Azerbaijan could spark new border conflicts. The Armenians' territorial claims and the suppression of Azerbaijanis in Armenia raised alarms within Azerbaijani society, leading to a surge in national sentiment. The union's leadership accused the Azerbaijan SSR leaders of fostering a nationalist agenda. These processes played a significant role in the national awakening in Azerbaijan. In the late 1950s, Moscow attempted to halt the national revival in Azerbaijan. However, despite the pressure and repression, the Soviet regime could not prevent the development of the national idea in Azerbaijan in the following decades, as the national revival left a lasting impact on the minds of the people. In 1959, Vali Akhundov became the head of Azerbaijan. Having served as the Minister of Health and chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR during the 1950s, Veli Akhundov was well-acquainted with the socio-political landscape, having actively participated in the Republic's developments. As a result, during his tenure, he was mindful of the country's political climate and adopted a more cautious approach than his predecessor, aiming to avoid provoking the central authorities. The national awakening in Azerbaijan continued throughout the 1960s.

V. Akhundov served as the head of the National Government of South Azerbaijan and passed away in 1947. He obtained permission from Moscow to lay Peshawari to rest in the Alley of Honor. In 1965, there was some reluctance to publish Peshawari's selected works and to name a street in Baku after him (Gasany, 2009). However, in 1966, Peshawari's selected works were finally published. During this period, there was a notable increase in patriotism among workers in the fields of science, literature, and culture. Particularly in the cultural sector, the concept of nationality took precedence over ideological dogmas. Efforts were made to take

an objective look at the events in Azerbaijan's history, especially in more recent centuries. Significant measures were implemented to preserve and revive national traditions.

When examining the events at the start of the 19th century, Azerbaijani historians moved away from the idea of Azerbaijan's "voluntary" annexation to Russia, instead characterizing it as a seizure based on historical facts. This significant event in Azerbaijan's history was analyzed by prominent historians such as Z. Bunyadaov, M. Ismailov, and S. Alyarov, whose evaluations caught the attention of the Republic's party leaders and security agencies (Gasanly, 2009). Soviet historical science, rooted in communist ideology and the rich traditions of statehood, portrayed the occupation policy of the Russian Empire as a well-structured strategy. It aimed to demonstrate, using "facts," that this policy positively influenced the development of the occupied regions. However, history was distorted, as the dismantling of Azerbaijani statehood, the influx of non-Azerbaijanis into the country, and the colonial policies of the Russian Empire were conveniently overlooked. The accurate evaluation of historical events from the 19th to 20th centuries was particularly perilous for the "Soviet reality," leading to efforts to suppress such assessments. Despite the official authorities' attempts and punitive measures, a more objective understanding of the nation's history was highly valued within society.

In the early 1960s, a significant student movement emerged in Azerbaijan, opposing Moscow's influence. The "People's Freedom Organization" founded in Baku in 1960, represented one of the efforts by the younger generation to resist this control (Qasimov, 2008). In the 1950s and 60s, while there was some moderation in the totalitarian Soviet regime, the reforms implemented did not alter the ideological foundations of the state. Taking advantage of the more relaxed political climate, the intelligentsia sought to promote ideas of national freedom among students and the youth. Given the impossibility of forming a mass organization to advocate for national ideas under a totalitarian regime, and with the memories of the repressions of the 1930s still fresh, free-thinking intellectuals established secret small groups dedicated to the promotion of National-Freedom ideas. However, these groups struggled to operate for long, as security agencies monitored all aspects of society, and their members faced repercussions.

In January 1966, a letter from Associate Professor S. Alyarov of Baku State University to the newspaper "Literature and Art" sparked significant public interest. In this letter, he proposed restoring the historical name of the city of Ganja. Back in 1935, the well-known Bolshevik S. Kirov had the city renamed Kirovabad in his honor, and it took considerable courage for Alyarov to initiate a discussion about reverting to the ancient name (Gasanly, 2009). This discussion did not yield the anticipated outcome. At that time, it was not possible

to restore the name of the ancient city of Ganja. However, the former name of another ancient Azerbaijani city was successfully reinstated. In 1968, the name of the city of Sheki was restored, which was met with public approval. The name of the city of Ganja was returned in 1989, coinciding with the surge of the popular movement in Azerbaijan.

Increased focus on national values was evident during this period. Shikhali Gurbanov, who held the position of secretary of the Central Committee of the AKP from 1966 to 1967, along with his supporters, played a significant role in this movement. For the youth with progressive ideas, the magazine “Ulduz” was launched in 1967. The Novruz holiday was celebrated under the title “Spring Holiday,” which helped to reinforce new national themes and a critical perspective in literature.

In the early 1960s, a group of open-minded students from Azerbaijan State University initiated a covert political movement led by Abulfaz Aliyev. On December 17, 1962, the “National Headquarters of Azerbaijan” (NAH) was formed during a secret meeting that included 95 participants. Regional departments of the organization were established, with many members being officials. The primary objective was to ensure that Azerbaijanis held leadership roles, to manage allocations to the Republic from Baku rather than Moscow, and to promote the National Awakening. The NAHs succeeded in securing the appointment of Azerbaijani officials to several key positions (Azərbaycan tarixi, 2008). During this time, the contributions of notable figures in science, literature, and music in Azerbaijan greatly influenced national identity and cultural growth. The celebration of Novruz in 1967 had a significant impact across the country. However, the pressure from the central government on the Republic's leadership intensified. As a result, it was not possible to officially celebrate Novruz in 1968.

In the 1960s, a dissident movement emerged in several Union republics of the Soviet Union, particularly in the Baltic States, Ukraine, and Russia. These dissidents advocated for human rights and minority issues while also criticizing the shortcomings of Soviet society. In the national republics, they further championed the cause of national freedom. The authorities were determined to suppress this dissident movement, which was not as prominent in Azerbaijan. There, the intelligentsia who held different views often expressed their opinions subtly, primarily through works of fiction. Heydar Aliyev, who held high-ranking positions in the State Security Committee of Azerbaijan and served as its chairman from 1967, played a significant role in protecting literary and scientific figures that faced persecution for their nationalist beliefs.

One of the individuals who helped him avoid criminal charges was Abulfaz Elchibey, who would later become the president of Azerbaijan. He was known for his radical nationalism during the Soviet era (Aliyev, 1989). In April 1966, coinciding with the anniversary of Azerbaijan's Sovietization in 1920, a group of young nationalists planning a large event was arrested but released after receiving stern warnings (XX əsr Azərbaycan tarixi, 2004). In the 1950s and 1960s, the Azerbaijani people engaged in a struggle to defend their right to use their language, preserve their national identity, and promote their culture. Those who emerged from this fight with dignity would encounter both significant achievements and considerable challenges in the following decades. The Azerbaijani people, who maintained the traditions of their national statehood, ultimately regained their independence at the end of the 20th century.

Azerbaijanis, a key ethno-political group in the South Caucasus, faced significant challenges from Tsarist Russia, which took control of the region in the 19th century, and from the imperial policies of the Soviet Union in the 20th century. Their Turkic-Muslim identity led to a harsher form of colonial oppression compared to their neighbors. The Azerbaijani language, culture, and traditions were under constant pressure, with assimilation policies being actively pursued. This included the resettlement of non-Azerbaijanis into Azerbaijan, the underrepresentation of Azerbaijanis in government roles, a lack of trust in them for important positions, and a neglect of their national and religious values. Armenians, who were well-represented in state structures sought to, leverage the Empire's colonial policies to their advantage. Despite facing significant ideological pressure, repression, and exile, the Azerbaijani people successfully maintained their national identity. In the 1950s and 1960s, the national awakening in Azerbaijan gained momentum, particularly in the early 1970s and 1980s. Under the leadership of national figure Heydar Aliyev, the country made remarkable strides in both cultural development and socio-economic progress. This period of National Awakening, which received a powerful boost, was crucial in the Azerbaijani people's fight for independence.

Conclusion

The totalitarian regime established in the Soviet Union, rooted in communist ideology, sought to forge an artificial Union known as the Soviet people. This was intended to be based on the national and cultural values, as well as the statehood traditions of the Russian people, who were the titular nation, by erasing national cultural distinctions. As a result, the rise of nationalist sentiments among non-Russian groups was viewed as a threat to the prevailing ideology and the very existence of the Soviet state. The development of culture in Azerbaijan has been crucial for safeguarding of national values. The fight for the Azerbaijani language's

status was vital in maintaining national identity. In the 1950s, the recognition of Azerbaijani as the state language and the creation of artistic works infused with national spirit helped bolster a sense of your mood. During the 1960s, intellectuals and students organized efforts to protect the country's national interests, seeking to assess Azerbaijan's historical events without ideological constraints. The celebration of Novruz as a spring festival and the restoration of Sheki's historical name demonstrate that the Azerbaijani people embrace their history and national identity, despite the pressures of the Soviet regime.

The dissident movement, led by the intelligentsia, emerged in Azerbaijan during this time. Participants of this movement openly criticized the anti-national elements of the Soviet system through their artistic works and in high school auditoriums, often urging young people to advocate for national ideas. Azerbaijani intellectuals, driven by a sense of national pride, played a significant role in the struggle for independence by passing on the ideals of national freedom to the younger generation.

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